

Research

China's Higher Education in the Eyes of African Senior Undergraduates Studying at Zhejiang Normal University

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Abstract: This study explores the understanding of African international senior undergraduates at Zhejiang Normal University about Chinese higher education (ZJNU). This research has conducted a qualitative approach, encompassed African international senior undergraduates at Zhejiang Normal University. Two sessions of 60 minutes focus group discussions (FGD) were used to explore the perspectives of China's Higher Education (CHE) through six senior African undergraduates from Tanzania, Namibia, Madagascar, DRC, Ghana and Gabon from three different departments at ZJNU. Findings showed that Chinese higher education is a bank of opportunities, the destination for international students, and Africans can afford it. Chinese higher education is getting more convincing and resilient because of personnel's solid motivation and engagement. Chinese higher education development is a massive progression in diplomacy between China and many other countries and is compatible with China's international status and policy purposes.

Keywords: China's higher education, international students, internationalization, globalization, scientific and technology innovation

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Introduction

A few decades ago, higher education passed under pressure from the increased demand growth for international students and the social, economic, political, and technical changes [1]. Higher education is the basis of holding development in a country and posing the future of a nation[2]. Each country has its system to develop its own higher education system to adequately respond to the needs of the country in terms of development. The educational system around many countries still follows the ancient and traditional system that was based on clear three separated levels such as primary education, secondary education, and higher education. When it comes to higher education, many

young people choose to leave their country to find a better education and spread across five continents and include various nationalities in every university worldwide [3].

Many youths now choose to study in Asia for many different reasons, and China is one of the most popular countries which recruits many international students in the Asian region [4]. Empirically, a country with excellent and robust higher education is significant for advancing its economic hegemony on many levels. More nations, such as China [5], the United States of America, France, Finland, and Australia, are involved in this education hegemony.

In China, universities compete to improve education and promote their international and domestic rankings. Having many international students in a university means that the university lives fully in globalization and internationalization. The number of international students studying reached 3000 in 2018 [6]. The topic of China's Higher education attracts many students' attention today because many questions are heard and seen that surprise many countries, for example: why is China the preferred destination for international students to study? Why China attracts many developing countries' attention? [7].

After implementing the opening-up policy, China has faced the reality of the rapid development of the economy and society. In education, China walked in the shadow of higher education internationalization. According to UNESCO's report on administration and management, Chinese public colleges and universities have been linked tightly with different levels of political administration [8]. Before, the Chinese Higher education system was highly characterized by the centralization of administration, in which decisions were from the central government. But after the reform, the situation quietly changed because the institutions' autonomy is increasingly seen increasing with efficient accountability and has re-naturalized the Chinese higher education system on a decentralization [8]. Indeed, the central government still controls and determines governance decentralization. Therefore, the provincial governments and higher institutions are granted more rights and autonomy. The mode of administration is less centralized but with tight cooperation between central and provincial governments [8]. Later more autonomy is granted for financial level, student recruitment, and course development. China's higher education has its nature, characteristics, dynamism, and autonomy concept, differentiating it from other countries.

In 2001, China joined the World Trade Organization. After joining, the Chinese government removed policy No 55 issued in 2000 about limiting the number of international students. Consequently, the number of international students in China increased faster and faster [9]. The international student flow was mainly oriented from the southern hemisphere countries to the northern hemisphere countries. In the case of Africa, according to the existing reality in recent years, the number of African students learning Chinese and studying in China has continued to increase to the exchanges between African countries and China, especially in the economic and Cultural fields. The Chinese Ministry of Education advanced that, in 2018, more than 81,000 African international students were studying in China, or 16.5%, compared to 49,792 in 2015 and 61,594 in 2016 [10]. The fact that international students are not aware of what is happening in the Chinese learning environment, learning engagement, and cultural differences may not attract some international students to come studying in China. And that's why this research was done [11].

Method of the study

The paper conducted focus group discussions (FGD) approach to explore the perspectives of China's Higher Education (CHE) through six senior African undergraduates from Tanzania, Namibia, Madagascar, DRC, Ghana, and Gabon from three different departments at ZJNU. The FGD process was scheduled in two sessions of 60 minutes, i.e., three participants during the first session and three for the second one. The session was separated to get more accurate information and to avoid confusion and boredom.

For interpretation, the FGD findings were coded as FGD_1 and FGD_2 . More importantly, during the two sessions, individual participants (IP) who shared some similar and dissimilar responses, due to that, coding technic was used, for example, IP_1 , IP_2 , etc., to protect their rights and information. And ($IP_{6;3;4}$) in case of response combination.

Apart from the FGD approach, this paper reviewed relevant documentation, reports, and articles to support and catalyze the study's completion. In addition, they show what the others have stated about the surroundings of this particular topic.

The objectives of the study

The aim is correspondingly to investigate the understanding of African senior undergraduate students at ZJNU in CHE, investigate the strengths and weaknesses of CHE, and finally share recommendations. To do so, the paper seeks to examine how African Senior Undergraduates Studying at ZJNU perceive China's Higher education by investigating its strength and weaknesses.

Results

Overview of international students at Zhejiang Normal University

According to the 2021 handbook provided by ZJNU, it is well-known in many disciplines and among those that produce the majority of teachers in China. ZJNU was founded in 1956 in Jinhua city, province of Zhejiang, in China. It is known as a provincial key University with 2800 faculty members and more than 3000 international students. It has been ranked in the top 100 among universities in China for eight consecutive years and ranks top 600 in World University Rankings [12].

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, China was already on its way to becoming a top destination for studying abroad. In 2018, China registered international students from different countries, particularly 196 countries. They were enrolled in 1,004 higher education institutions [13]. Consequently, the number of international students had double when 238,184 were enrolled. In the case of China, according to the ministry of Education 2022, *"the gross enrollment rate of China's higher education hit 57.8 percent in 2021, compared with 30 percent in 2012. Over 44.3 million students are studying at higher education institutions across the country, which put China currently has the world's most extensive higher education system."*[14]

Fig. 1: The increasing development of the number of international students studying in China from 2003 to 2018.

Participants' reasons for choosing Chinese higher education institutions

According to many statements, China is among the top in sending their students to study abroad. However, this statement was criticized and debated rapidly a few years ago, making China a country receiving international students [15]. At the same time, China is currently a multiple sending and receiving country for international students and has increasingly become the largest destination for international students from developing countries [16].

As the $IP_{3;5;1}$ affirmed

“...We came to study in China because China has become the new bank of opportunities, new destination flows, and mobility for international students to study. Also, because of many interests like the internationalization of Chinese Higher Education, the quality of education that China has, facilities, infrastructures, etc. And almost all the participants affirmed this because of China’s rapid economic development and future development prospects.”

These answers about China's rapid development, rapid economic development, and China's bright future were almost mentioned in each participant's responses during interviews and even during the focus discussion. In addition, compared to other developed or developing countries, in terms of school fees China has cheaper school fees that many foreign students can afford especially Africans.

In this relation, almost all participants stated that

“We came to China to study because they are giving us many opportunities, such as affordable school fees, rapid services, and proposed many types of scholarship that in other countries it is quite complex and difficult to get them.”

On the other hand, respondents from French-speaking countries affirmed that a few years ago, the French government planned to significantly increase university tuition fees for foreigners, sowing concern among African students. China, on the contrary, is reaching out to them.

“Now, China is the second most popular destination for African students. However, there are already English-speaking African students who know longtime ago about China's situation, which has become their first destination to study, especially from South-East Africa.”

These statements have reconfirmed the information from IIE’s reports that show China is the new destination for international students and can compete with any country. In 2015, China overtook Germany and France for homing international students, homing 8% of them, and classified as third after the United States of America and the United Kingdom.

Table 1: The IIE’s report on the ranking and proportion of the top countries’ destination of international students

The top destination countries of international students over the world	
United State of America (USA)	22%
United Kingdom (UK)	11%
China	8%
Germany	7%
France	7%

Source: IIE’s report, 2015

According to Table 1, we can advance a pre-conclusion that affirms China can rank in line with western developed countries and European countries. In addition, it is even ranked in third position leaving behind Germany and France. However, China's Government expectation for a Plan to Study in China wanted the number of international students studying in Mainland China to be 500,000 by 2020. In 2018, the number of international students in Mainland China was 492,185 from 196 countries, presenting a remarkable increase of 3,013 students (0.62%) compared to the previous year, 2017 [17]. Therefore, 240 million people in China have received higher education so far [18].

China’s Higher Education Landscape

For historical comparison, unlike western countries and their tradition, Chinese universities were almost entirely controlled and determined by the Chinese central government before the Chinese higher education reform, which caused a lack of autonomy at certain levels [19]. However, post-reform, tremendous independence, and self-determination were seen at certain levels, leading to a unique Chinese higher education label. IIEP’s report in 2014

qualifies as a paradox of the centralized decentralization of Higher education [8]. At some level, a partial integration with the government is observed. Whereas, Western universities are constantly separated between the university and the State. Higher education in China is the most tremendous worldwide. Historically, China faced many challenges before achieving its current stage.

From the dynasty period till now, China's Higher education has never ceased to be objectively improved. The traditional higher education during the Qing dynasty was replaced by a modern system which resulted in the introduction of the Western education system. It impacted the other social reforms in the late Qing dynasty [20]. In the early 21st century, Chinese higher education experienced a considerable expansion from the elite status to the massification stage.

In terms of enrollment, it has consistently increased gradually. This expansion of student enrolment is accompanied by a growth in the number of higher education institutions and the average scale of enrolment per institution [21]. According to the 2015 Statistical Bulletin on the Development of the National Education Enterprise released by the MOE in July 2016, *"There was a total of 292 adult Higher Education Institutions with 6,359,400 total enrollments, 2,367,500 freshmen, and 2,362,600 graduates in the year of 2015."* [20].

It is known that China currently has the world's most extensive higher education system. By the end of 2016, China had registered 2,880 higher education institutes, and there is an augmentation of 90 more compared to 2012. The ministry stated that these institutions had almost 37 million students, an 11.2% increase from five years ago. Furthermore, China has focused and paid great attention to deepening international cooperation in education. The country has built ties with 188 countries and regions and has ratified agreements on mutual recognition of academic degrees with 47 countries and regions. Indeed, Li Hai, the ministry's deputy director of international cooperation and exchanges, affirmed that

"With 545,000 students overseas last year, China has become the world's largest source of international students". Further, "there were 442,000 students from 205 countries and regions in China last year, making China the largest destination in Asia for overseas study" [22].

Evidence shows that 2,738 public colleges and universities, with around 32.9 million students, were enrolled in China, including 1,270 universities and 1,468 higher vocational colleges [23].

The institutional education system comprises bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degrees, and non-degree programs, which are widely open to international students [24]. However, mainland China has been the most crucial source country for countless international students for decades. As the Chinese Ministry of Education (MOE) affirmed (2017),

"Over 600,000 Chinese students are determined to proceed with their higher education abroad. With the rising demand from Chinese students for a more diverse educational experience, meanwhile, colleges and universities across the world are also establishing their existence in China." [25] affirms *"the task of higher education is not restricted only to fostering the economic enlargement of nations and offering opportunities to individuals but extends more particularly to the promotion of cultural diversity, political democracy, and trade."*

Numerous scholars and researchers have emphasized that higher education can naturally be used to serve society and promote international cooperation if put on the right pathway. However, Chinese higher education focuses on trends and patterns of students and staff's cross-border mobility, education business growth, research publications and research concentrations, ICT connectivity, the language of use, and cross-border political flows. From that part, national higher education worldwide constantly plays a decisive factor in the national establishment; Chinese higher education is no exception.

China's Higher education is an intrinsic sector of the nation-building project. It contributes to a remarkable component of China's strategic policy initiative to reinforce national strength or pillar through science and education.

Reformed to develop its higher education system of international scope, this is the strategy the government has employed to achieve impressive results. Though across the national programs such as 211 and 985, China has specifically selected the best universities for in-depth investment, intending to make them world-class in decades and be more conducive to reform development and scientific development. It has been proven with precision worldwide that this introduced plan and the support given to the higher education institution, especially Tsinghua University in China, has grown and accelerated its development and has and/or responds continuously to the dynamic of innovations in the context of globalization and internationalization.

According to the FGD₂, the landscape of Chinese higher education,

"Our point of view regarding higher education in China, it's difficult for us to define. Still, the simple, visible, and tangible things are that higher education in China is developing a lot and can compete well with the famous universities outside. The ranking of these Chinese universities worldwide can confirm and answer what higher education looks like in China, such as Tsinghua University, Beijing University, Zhejiang University, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, etc. If we only look at the infrastructure of our university, it is well-equipped. We can assert that higher education in China is profound. As evidence, if Chinese higher education has inadequate facilities and equipment, international students won't come here to study if the quality is terrible. The existence of many international students is enough to judge its quality because no one will spend resources on useless or fake things. In my case, I will not come here if I hear bad things about their higher education."

Globalization and internationalization of Higher Education

Globalization and internationalization are the essential elements, powerful and famous words of higher education evolution [26]. The Globalization of Higher education and the massive growth of international students enrolled in different universities are stated [27]. By simple definition, *"Globalization is the interconnectedness of people and businesses worldwide that eventually leads to global cultural, political, and economic integration. In addition, it is the ability to move and communicate easily with others worldwide to conduct business internationally"* [28]. The practice of internationalization focuses more on the international dimensions of higher and postsecondary education. It is interpreted differently by different stakeholders in other countries. International student recruitment became popular in higher education and led non-native-speaking English countries to amend their higher education system to attract more international students [29].

The research discovered,

"Most of all international students have chosen English-speaking countries because of the power of the English language, which is still the first communication language used by many countries. Currently, many foreign students go to China because of globalization and internationalization of China's higher education."

In addition, China is on the way to spreading its language and culture; more and more international students are getting interested in the Chinese language. Using the Chinese language after the English language is gaining a better place in research and publishing. Therefore, research and publishing are essential tools for disseminating Chinese scholarly voices and culture worldwide [30]. Furthermore, the existence of Confucius institutes marks also the instruments of spreading the Chinese language and its culture. IP₂; 6 admitted that

"The presence of Confucius institutes in many countries already means the openness and concrete proof of the internationalization of Chinese higher education. Nowadays, the Chinese language competes with the English language because the number of people interested in learning the Chinese language is increasing yearly. Moreover, Chinese is classified as a commercial language because most people involved in business learn, understand, and know Chinese. For instance, Zhejiang Normal University has many international students in the language department, especially those who choose to study Chinese."

Before, these two terms were massively dominated by western countries spreading their superpowers. Still, this view has deviated to other angles and is dominated by all countries, especially China, after their policy of opening up in 1949.

*IP*_{1;4;6} stated,

“The globalization and internationalization era are considered a dedicated era for preparing the future of youth by exchanging the culture, communication, experiences, and the age of the dissemination of goods. Indeed, these two aspects massively influence the minds of youths. Sometimes the globalization and internationalization of higher education may not be suitable for developing countries because the young people who study abroad do not return to their origin. Also, it has increased the student’s mobility, and those who have completed their studies don’t want to go home as they enjoy the new life they see in the place where they study.”

*FGD*_{1,2} asserted,

“Patriotism is needed to deal with globalization and internationalization for the benefit of a country. Accepting globalization and internationalization is not a bad thing. Still, if the students who study abroad have no accountability and responsibility, the country and government they came from will be defeated. Developing countries should imitate what China is doing when it comes to going to study abroad because most of the Chinese students who go to study overseas go home after finishing their studies. This reflects patriotism because they want to apply what they learned in other countries to their respective country.”

Promotion of scientific and technological innovation in China

One of the most important motives that have pushed China and Chinese universities is the promotion of research, the research outcome publications, and research fruit valorization. That is why many Chinese universities are included in the top 1000 universities in the world. This factor attracts many students and scholars from all over the world to study in China. Many Chinese students and teachers are very committed to research, and the Chinese government and teachers with experience approvingly invest and closely monitor it.

Affirmed by the *IP*_{2;4;5;6}

“The progress of technology in China is fast. In our university, we use many technologies; everything we do and uses here is electronic, for example, in the office, in the canteens, and almost everywhere. Every year there is something new, and sometimes we find it difficult to use because it is too advanced. All this results from scientific growth and technological innovations, a significant feature that distinguishes it from other places.”

After the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China (NCCPC) in 2012, the government would do everything possible to help and promote the research as soon as possible to strengthen national research. The government accounted that innovation in technology and scientific research drives productivity and boosts national power [31]. Research, science, and technology innovation are the top national development priorities. In addition, they accounted that one of the best ways to reach the highest level of research and innovations and to be part of the international competitor is to consider the science and technology development trends.

*IP*_{3;6} stated,

“The Chinese leaders are very loyal to their teachers and researchers and allow them to do many different types of research to focus on the progress that depends on research. Research and publication results are one of the tasks faculties that must be done. Research has flourished in science, technology, humanities, and social sciences during the current existence of covid-19.”

Kang (2021) has confirmed that: “the strength of university research ability is of considerable significance to the country’s innovation capacity” [32]. China has two ways of assuring higher education: first, promoting innovation trans-

formation through cooperation with enterprises to improve innovation ability [33]. In addition, high-ranking universities have considerably enhanced and upgraded the innovation performance of enterprises. And the second is to promote innovation by producing high-quality human capital and a highly skilled labor force [34]. It can be inferred that a new generation of science and technology will lead the future of the research system. Therefore, this point of view reflects mainstream trends and the direction of the current scientific and technological revolution.

After implementing the opening-up policy in China, a new wave of scientific and technological revolution was rapidly emerging and demonstrated by the following features: Major developments in scientific research are in view, and current scientific systems have emerged. In addition, a model revolution in science, technology, and innovation occurred, triggering significant changes in research organizations and leading to more research and innovation activities. Furthermore, scientific and technological innovation is complex and significantly impacts economic and social development. Therefore, gradually it will destroy the old productive forces and strengthen the tension between the traditional institutional system and the new social productive forces. It could conclude the creation of new requirements for innovation worldwide in the science and technology system.

As an anticipated summary, global competition remains majoritarian among all superpower countries, especially in science and technology, and is still escalating daily. And China already becomes an essential participant in worldwide science and technology governance, even if China is still confronted with many challenges.

Strengths of China's Higher Education

China is an innovation-driven country, and the re-engagement in innovation is highlighted in the outline of the national medium and long-term program for the reform and development of education (2010- 2020) [31]. The nation has attainments and long-standing devotion to innovation and higher education, comprising serving its government, which impressed early Western countries [35]. Striving for world-class universities has been singled out as one of China's fundamental political positions. Considering that first-class universities, it has gradually impacted a nation's broad influence. Additionally, among the powerful tactic that the Chinese government introduced is that they committed advantageously promoting and/or sponsoring other Chinese universities with the potential to join the world-class league and empowering them comprehensively [36]. The appeal to have worldwide competitive universities provides the impetus for China's best universities to follow and benchmark the means of European and North American universities [37]. For instance, from curriculum to financial practices/services to new governance organizations, which will naturally imply transformations in the reference structure of higher education policy to also encompass international standards, particularly at the higher level of universities. Evidence demonstrates that China's higher education policy and the system pay special attention to its country's development and its citizens' social life through governance and/or administration within higher education [38].

Accordingly, in China, sciences, research innovation, appropriate equipment, competitive-ness, and acquiring solid educational policy (for teachers, staff, and students) or beyond are among the essential features that support China's higher education development, even in the present era. For instance, China has the second-highest number of universities in the world in the 2018 academic ranking of the world's top 500 universities [39]. As evidenced by National Science Foundation, National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics; SRI International; Science-Metrix; Elsevier, Scopus abstract and citation database, in 2017, China surpassed the United States with the highest number of scientific publications [40]. Various researchers assert that higher education in China has diverse assets. This study, however, underlines the research publication policy, which is one of the foremost in Chinese higher education and contributes to its excellent global reputation.

All these confirm that higher education in China has its specificity. Despite all these facts, the interviews demonstrate that many things can be said, that many factors can be said about the power of Chinese higher education.

IP_{3;5,6} affirmed,

“As it has always been a part of the productive force of China's development in each way, the practical method is regarded as the driving force for advancing its achievements so far, which is less theory and more practice. Undoubtedly, China is a powerful country that ranks first ahead of the United States and is sufficiently well-equipped and endowed with resources to develop its higher education constantly. However, it continually puts its tradition, culture, and the well-being of its society ahead of all programs they undertake, for instance, merging these aspects into the curriculum. The pedagogy is one of the fundamental strengths that made Chinese education so productive and effective, which is worth learning from other higher education institutions.”

IP_{1, 4, 5, 2} also asserted,

“The real strength of Chinese higher education can be seen in maturity, honesty, and integrity. These three elements are found in Chinese universities. For instance, at ZJNU, all the daily schedules set by all the leaders are respected from registration day to deadline, vacation time, and all the activities that must be done during the year. The delay is not frequently seen; student and teacher strike and government instability as well. We have not heard of students and teachers protest since we arrived here.”

As *IP₃* affirmed:

“In my view, solid motivation brought strength to Chinese higher education because it is evident that the Chinese are very motivated, whether teachers or students, when they promote something and have a competitive nature too. This strong motivation and competitive spirit have accelerated and strengthened Chinese universities.”

Weaknesses of China' Higher Education

After the FGD1;2, China' Higher Education faces the same challenges as other countries' higher education. China has weaknesses despite its excellent quality of resources in terms of infrastructure, budget, academic programs, researchers, learners, teachers, and others. Indeed, some tiny weaknesses might be a drawback, yet it is reflected as a non-blockage of their higher education to be developed but should be needed more attention. That is, the development abroad should not stop at the presence of Confucius, especially in African countries, but should be drawn from several branches so that the students who cannot go to China can choose other things to study apart from the Chinese language.

The same goes for the Chinese students who should come in large numbers to study in these new and famous universities in all these developing countries. For instance, it is empirically known that fewer Chinese learners come to developing countries to study to share mutual experiences.

Nowadays, it is found that there are three main issues considered as blockage of China's higher education [20]:

- Firstly, to continue with the gradual expansion of higher education at the three levels, promoting the massification of China's higher education;
- Secondly, to restructure the relationships between the three levels to better adjust to the increasingly changing needs of the labor market (the workforce demands of the high, medium, and low levels);
- Finally, to focus on shaping the features of specialized higher education or short-cycle higher education as a unique educational level, to expand education leading to professional degrees.

Therefore, there was a structural adjustment of the disciplines made by China's higher education, and it was more focused on these three following issues:

- regulate the ratio of social science, humanities, science, and engineering disciplines according to market demands, and regulate equally the proportion of applied science disciplines to major science disciplines;
- expand in more extent the scope and number of applied science specialties (e.g., computer science, life sciences) and their programs, responding globally to the growing market needs for labor in these popular disciplines and specialties;

- carrying on the periodic review of disciplines and specialties to reduce redundant configuration of disciplines in HEIs.

In contrast, the findings revealed,

“Even though China has its challenges in spreading its language, it should continuously develop more in the majors taught in the English language. Because one of the aspects that make international students fear going to China is their inability to speak Chinese, especially those a little older. But for those still very young, learning the language is not a problem because they are young and still have time.

From what we heard from some of our foreign friends, there are courses they do not attend because of their inability to speak Chinese. As a result, the courses have to be canceled for some. Therefore, there should be different translations of the same books that the students use. Many Chinese books indeed have English translations, but this should be expanded, strengthening the internationalization that is being done in higher education.”

Suggestions for China’ Higher Education development

China has found and achieved all the requirements as evidence of having advanced and developed higher education. According to respondent 4, being an international student from Africa, it is better to suggest and focus more on the circumstance regarding both countries, China-Africa. These are the suggestions that might be crucial in the point to promote more China’s Higher Education development, as follows:

-Promote knowledge sharing between African and Chinese citizens as uplifting knowledge sharing is one of the substantial research items and a large contest. Hence, there is a need to cement a sincere and truthful relationship between Africans and Chinese, which implies that knowledge sharing should be smoothed and encouraged.

-The two nations need to pay attention to the benefits and value of possessed knowledge by others. The prospect of sharing strong knowledge is a guaranteed constituent of the extent that means valuable and practical learning at a higher education institution.

-Commonly, Africans and Chinese must believe their mutual relations can be upgraded and toughened through joint knowledge sharing. One party should not only wait for another party to do so, but both parties should also vigorously contribute to the exchange of ideas

-African and Chinese should increase and strengthen communication, exchanges, and reciprocity to create a strong social network between African and Chinese students. It means engaging the willingness to communicate our skills and abilities, engaging in intellectual debates and discussions

On the other hand, according to all respondents,

“It should be greater if teachers and professors share their experiences in the sense of exchanging teachers’ experiences. For instance, sending foreign teachers to China versus sending Chinese teachers to other countries to teach. Besides, the policy toward international students should be less solid regarding the internship to attract more students and push the flow of mobility.”

Figure 2: Summarize of African students’ recommendation from Chinese Higher Education

Discussions

It’s worth noticing that we can anticipate that Chinese higher education is on its way to becoming more potent and has its proper strength because of all the efforts made that are improving and progressing every year. Accordingly, the current form of Chinese higher education differs from the past. Previously, the central government managed all the university affairs. And presently, institutions have some self-rule under the management of the government. After the opening up, internationalization and decentralization of higher education emerged and were implemented.

Indeed, all the efforts made in Chinese higher education are proven in their ranks. Chinese universities can compete well with Western universities even though they have only flourished recently. The power of Chinese universities has occurred, and they are very competitive internationally. It is undeniable and cannot be hidden the determination, honesty, and integrity in the matter of management in Chinese higher education.

As summary from the interviewees, many countries are convinced of the quality and maturity of Chinese universities. For instance, in financial terms, students from all developing countries can afford tuition, books, assurance, dormitory, etc. Furthermore, they feel satisfied with all the facilities and equipment used in Chinese universities. Higher education has come a long way regarding research development because Chinese research is at the forefront of science, technology, and engineering. China spent and still spends many capital resources for its research and development, which is increasingly flourishing yearly. As evidence, the Ministry of Science and Technology declared that China's gross domestic research and development (R&D) expenditure grew from 1.03 trillion yuan (\$153 billion) to the world's second-largest of 2.79 trillion yuan (\$414.3 billion) between 2012 to 2021. The ratio of R&D spending to GDP rose from 1.91 to 2.44 percent. Therefore, basic research expenditure in 2021 was 3.4 times that of 10 years ago, accounting for about 6.09 percent of total R&D expenditure, a record high for China [41]. Therefore, the internationalization of higher education in China is very deep-rooted and key to the success of higher education. As a result of the growth of higher education, Chinese development is fast, and China has become a superpower at many levels because Chinese leaders value teachers and researchers. On the other hand, higher education and its prosperity are the foundation of all development and the country's future. Interestingly, higher education has become a destination for international students from many countries worldwide.

Conclusion

This study highlighted China's higher Education in the eyes of African senior undergraduates at ZJNU. It obviously can contradict or confirm the prejudices and judgments of others on China's Higher Education. Chinese higher Education has faced and still faces many challenges as it competes internationally. It has been identified that the higher education policy encountered a considerable transformation after the opening-up: Chinese higher education responses and key to Chinese development. China's higher Education plays a significant role in modern society and quasi-meets the demand of international students even if many changes are still required.

China has changed its history. The mobility and flow of international students in China is a positive development and a massive progression in diplomacy between China and many other countries. Therefore, the Education given and received by international students is in line and compatible with China's purposes for its international status and policy. Whatever the government's efforts to achieve, they must always accentuate the action on the development of internationalization according to the demand and should consider the critics from different angles.

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